

Design of tilted grating coupler array for a photonic-integrated FMCW LiDAR PIC

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we propose a new concept for LiDAR Photonic integrated circuits that is based on tilted grating coupler that doesn't require any phase modulators for beam steering. Our simulations for SOI waveguide structure show that the concept of tilted grating coupler is feasible with a FOV of 100° by 35°

Keywords: Optical Phased Arrays, Grating Coupler, LiDAR, Beam shaping and steering.

1. INTRODUCTION

Photonic integration is a promising technology able to provide compact low-power and affordable Frequency-Modulated-Continuous-Wave (FMCW) LiDAR systems¹². The advantages of making the LiDAR onchip are the smaller footprint and the large scale fabrication capacity which leads to the reduction of manufacturing cost per system. Onchip LiDAR does not require mechanical parts for beam steering, make optical phased arrays (OPA) a very attractive candidate for LiDAR applications. The beam forming in Optical Phased Arrays are similar to the beam forming of conventional phased arrays in radar systems, the beam is formed by constructive interference of the radiation from the emitting elements. The steering of the beam is achieved by gradually tuning the phase of light propagating in the waveguide elements, through thermo-optic or electro-optic phase shifters, which can increase the complexity of the device. In this paper we propose a new concept based on tilted grating couplers 1.

2. TILTED GRATING COUPLER ARRAY

The proposed architecture is based on pure passive structures, as it does not require OPAs or a large number of individually-controlled phase shifters to accomplish 3D environmental mapping. Furthermore, we simultaneously illuminate and measure the light received from all angular directions to reduce the capture time of the point cloud. Figure 1 illustrates the concept of our proposed FMCW LiDAR PIC which is based on tilted grating couplers. The concept relies on transmitting multiple beams towards all directions through a transmitter grating coupler (TxGC) and receiving the signal reflected from a target using a receiver (RxGC) located directly next to the Tx-GC.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the FMCW LiDAR PIC showing the linear array of gradually-tilted grating couplers and simulated farfield pattern from the structure of equally spaced 33 elements.

A cylindrical lens system 6a is used to collimate the beam from the Tx-GC to achieve a very small diffraction angle. Similarly, an incoming signal from the same direction will focus on the Rx-GC situated directly next to the Tx-GC. Figure 2a shows a schematic of the complete FMCW Li-DAR PIC. Light from a fast-tunable laser is divided by a star coupler among all the Tx-GCs. Each Tx-GC then radiates the light out of the PIC toward one specific direction determined by the tilting of the grating coupler and is collimated by the cylindrical lens. After reflection from a target, the light is reflected to the PIC in the same direction, and therefore focused by the lens on almost the same location as the Tx-GC. After the Rx-GC, the incoming signal is mixed with a portion of the signal that was left over after the Tx-GC in a broadband directional coupler and guided towards the balanced detector. Photodetectors are either flip chipped on top of the chip, or integrated on the chip.

2.1 Tilted Grating Coupler Design

In order to test the feasibility of our architecture and calculate the field-of-view (FOV), we have simulated the slanted grating coupler performance for the SOI waveguide structure shown in the figure 2a.

Figure 2. a) Illustration of the slanted GC waveguide structure. b) Top view of proposed grating coupler structure: θ is the tilted angle of the grating teeth and Λ is the period. κ zenith direction of radiation and ϕ azimuth direction of radiation.

Fig. 2b shows top view of the slanted grating coupler illustrating how the tilt in the grating coupler was introduced.

Fig. 3a shows the relation between the GC tilt angle theta and the radiation direction (see figure 1). Fig. 3b shows the far-field pattern of slanted GC for 2 different positive and negative slanting angles. This result shows that the radiation angle can be shifted up to $\pm 50^\circ$ by tilting the gratings up to $\pm 16^\circ$ before the radiated power starts dropping (see fig. 3c). For this implementation in SOI technology only 30% is radiated upward, and therefore for future implementations more directional grating couplers are preferred such as the ones described in. 3

Figure 3. a) Radiation angle versus tilt of the grating. b) Farfield pattern for 0 +16 -16 degrees. c) Simulated optical powers coupled out of the grating couplers in all direction.

Fig. 4 shows the steering of the radiation angle in the azimuth direction ϕ which is controlled by the wavelength of the laser. This plot shows that the steering in this direction is limited to around 35° when changing the wavelength by 240nm.

To capture the maximum light along the z axis the length of the grating coupler was also calculated for different directions and radiations and for etch depths of 5nm and 10nm. The simulations show that it's possible

Figure 4. Simulated diffraction angle versus wavelength.

to have a transmission in forward direction around 20% if the etching depth is 10nm.⁴ The focusing of the cylindrical lens is 3mm long 6b, hence desired length of the grating coupler is achieved to gather maximum light along the z direction.

Figure 5. The desired length of 3mm for 5nm and 10nm etch depth.

3. OPTICAL SYSTEM

In order to focus light at uniform distance on top of every single Rx Gc a fixed focal length mobile phone camera lens system was investigated (Fig. 6) using Zemax simulation software.⁵ The size of camera lens is relatively small only 6.53mm which allows to make the system more compact. The simulated camera lens system can focus light from $\pm 35^\circ$.

The width of the RxGc-s are calculated from the $1/e^2$ of point spread functions from the focused collimated beams at different angles.

From the simulated lens we can find the number of the Rx grating couplers with the width of RxGC $10\mu\text{m}$ and the gap of $0.5\mu\text{m}$ is 421. Hence taking into account the lens $\text{FOV} = 70^\circ$ the angular resolution of 0.166° is achieved.

4. CONCLUSION

The tilted grating coupler array concept for FMCW or ToF LiDAR have proposed and evaluated. Tilted grating coupler architecture was discussed and the numerical results were shown We have simulated a field-of-view of 100° by 35° , with the number of $\text{Tx}=\text{Rx}=421$ and angular resolution of 0.166° . Our architecture offers many advantages over existing LiDAR architectures, such as highly scalable, flexibility of implementation on any waveguide platform since the laser and photodetectors can be placed off-chip. It can be implemented both with FMCW and ToF LiDAR systems. The future direction of the research is to fabricate and characterize the tilted grating array which performs the best and meets the industry requirements.

Figure 6. a) extruded lens system b) Focusing of investigated camera along the z axis. c) Width at $1/e^2$ of the focused beam

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